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Preface

This special issue is dedicated to our colleague Veronika Novakova who we have longer or shorter privilege of knowing in our professional or personal lives. Once this crazy idea originated during one of the coffee meetings of our group, I was slightly skeptic of how many contributions we will be able to collect. And of course, I was afraid that the issue will look a bit slim if we will have just one or two papers only from our group (or those people who I can personally and physically force to write something). However, I was extremely surprised how positive and enthusiastic were the responses of all people who we contacted with this crazy request of writing some contribution celebrating her 40th anniversary. I think that all these contributors did it with a great pleasure since they know Veronika or remember her as very kind, willing, helping, and unselfish person although sometimes a bit self-underestimating (that we do not clearly understand why, and some research should be done on this topic). Happy birthday, Veru!

Petr Zimčík, editor of the special issue

Hradec Králové, 24 January 2023

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Child-induced DNA Damage in the Female Brain after Age 40

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Special issue on the occasion of 40th birthday of Veronika Nováková

ABSTRACT: The ageing of the female brain is a cause of cognitive decline in the elderly and the major risk factor for them becoming an obnoxious, insufferable old crones. The time in life when brain ageing begins is undefined. Here we show that transcriptional profiling of the female frontal cortex from individuals ranging from 26 to 106 years of age having 0-7 children defines a set of genes with reduced expression after age 40 and after having 1 or more children. These genes play central roles in synaptic plasticity, mitochondrial function, alcohol metabolism, ability to tolerate noise and overall well-being. This is followed by induction of stress response to children, men and essentially all living creatures. DNA damage is markedly increased in the promoters of genes with reduced expression in the aged cortex, assuming the female brain has any. Moreover, these gene promoters are selectively damaged by kitchen- and children's playroom-induced stress in cultured female neurons, and show reduced base-excision hangover repair. Thus, DNA damage may reduce the expression of selectively vulnerable genes involved in learning, memory and every day survival, initiating a programme of brain ageing that starts after age 40.¹

Happy Birthday, Veru!

Reference:

1. Tao Lu, Ying Pan, Shyan-Yuan Kao, Cheng Li, Isaac Kohane, Jennifer Chan & Bruce A. Yankner. Gene regulation and DNA damage in the ageing human brain. *Nature* 429 (2004), 883–891. .

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Coming to Sunny Spain to Harvest Light

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ABSTRACT: Veronika has been always interested in PDT and phthalocyanine analogues. She wanted to learn more about phthalocyanines and experience how life is like in a sunny country. She decided to join Tomas Torres's group in Madrid, one of best places in the world wherein you can enjoy both phthalocyanines and sun, and improve your photosensitization abilities She realized that indeed life in a sunny country is very pleasant, but our group enjoy also her luminous character. Veronika, we are happy to keep in touch with you and meet each other every ICPP. We wish you a very happy birthday and a prosperous, healthy, and brilliant decade.

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New Element Discovered for Its Unique Interactions with Azaphthalocyanines

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, we present our recent studies of azaphthalocyanines in particle accelerator that led to discovery of *Veronicium* (Vr). The observed results were not compatible with our quantum mechanics models for known cations. Further tests proved presence of azaphthalocyanine complexes with Vr²⁺ cations. The quantum mechanics calculations supporting our experimental data were performed using novel methods because the new element involves orbitals that were not included in the state-of-the-art methods.

Later, studies showed that the obtained element can be naturally found in the Pilsen region of Czech Republic and the corresponding carbon dating technique confirmed the presence of Vr from January 1983 ± 200 years. Following these initial data, our group from the Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove identified Vr in Hradec Kralove and its energetic presence has been happily felt for the past 21 years. The element is highly stable in AzaPc laboratory and can withstand any extreme conditions including manuscript revisions and grant deadlines. The mighty Vr is still at her sweet 16, with an additional 24 years of experience in studenthood, wifehood, parenthood, and mentorship.

In fact, when searching literature, we have discovered by happy accident, that such extraordinary element's inevitable existence was predicted early after the periodic table was established. Although, at the time, the authors could not have foreseen its completely unique and all-encompassing properties, they properly assumed it as an indispensable part of the universe [1].

The first confirmed element of the 8th row of the periodic table was named *Veronicium* after our dearest friend and colleague Veronika Nováková. Happy birthday, Veronika!

References:

[1] Cimrman J. et al. *Chemische Perspektiven*, 1(1), 1-50.

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Chocolate and Beer Consumption, Cognitive Function, and Nobel Laureates or Excellent Scientists

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ABSTRACT: Dietary flavonoids, abundant in plant-based foods such as chocolate, have been shown to improve cognitive function. Since chocolate consumption could hypothetically improve cognitive function not only in individuals but also in whole populations, we wondered whether there would be a correlation between a country's level of chocolate consumption and its population's cognitive function. To our knowledge, no data on overall national cognitive function are publicly available. Conceivably, however, the total number of Nobel laureates per capita could serve as a surrogate end point reflecting the proportion with superior cognitive function and thereby give us some measure of the overall cognitive function of a given country.

We found that there is a close, significant linear correlation ($r = 0.791$, $P < 0.0001$) between chocolate consumption per capita and the number of Nobel laureates per 10 million persons in a total of 23 countries. Switzerland was the top performer in terms of both the number of Nobel laureates and chocolate consumption. Strikingly, when recalculated with the combined consumption of chocolate and beer per capita, the correlation coefficient increased to 0.934. This coefficient increased to 0.99 when the age is limited to the group of quadragenarian women. As the result, we can predict, without the doubt, that assoc. prof. Veronika Nováková is among the small group with significant chance to obtain prestigious grant, scientific award or breakthrough research paper in the near future. Increased consumption of beer and chocolate would turn this probability into a certainty, with Oracle of Delphi predicted that the best day for such increase consumption to January 24, 2023. On the other hand, it should be mentioned and warned that increased consumption of beer and chocolate in other investigated group of quadragenarian led in some cases to promotion to prestigious positions in respective institutions, which, however, led to complete withdrawal from a scientifically productive life, such as in the case of Peter the Builder Zimčík or Kačka the Big Boss Vávrová.

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Universal Multi Sensors Based on Azaphthalocyanine Dyes

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ABSTRACT: With the advances in sensor technology and the increasing quantity of multi-sensors, multi-temporal, and multi-resolution data from different sources, azaphthalocyanine compounds have become as definitively the best tool in sensing applications. The main objective of this contribution is to synergistically combine data from different channels of visible luminescence (from blue to red) with different characteristics, resolution, and quality in order to provide more reliable, accurate, and useful information required for effective planning and cool decision-making. The topics of interest include (but are not limited to): COVID 19 sensing, gender/sex sensing, family relation sensing, and remote sensing of amazing places on Earth. Special thanks to Veronika for the inspiration to select the azaphthalocyanine derivatives for the research.

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Design of Novel Supramolecular Macroheterocyclic Multimetallic VErONiKA's Assembly

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ABSTRACT: Novel supramolecular macroheterocyclic multimetallic assembly have been designed starting from two low symmetry tripyrazinoporphyrazines bearing fused 1,2,5-selenadiazole and 4,5-dioxobenzene fragments (V^{IV} and Er^{III} complexes, respectively) and incorporate also Ni^{II} complex of 5,10,15-triarylpyrazino[b]porphyrin, diaza-18-crown-6 and As^{III} phthalocyanine subunits. The assembly of the bisporphyrazine fragment (V-Er) can be conducted using reductive deselenation of 1,2,5-selenadiazole derivative followed by pyrazine bridge formation in the condensation reaction the intermediate vicinal diaminoderivative with o-benzoquinone containing tripyrazinoporphyrazine. Pd-catalyzed coupling reaction might be used for connection meso-brominated Ni(II) phenyl porphyrin with As(III) phthalocyanine complex containing 4-bromophenyl by diaza-18-crown-6 linker with formation (Ni-crown-As). The presence of meso-4-hydroxyphenyl substituent allows its axial ligation to the Er atom through phenolic O atom affording in the presence of KOH as a base the final multimetallic pentamacroheterocyclic supermolecule which we name V-Er-O-Ni-K-As molecule. This molecules which should have almost panchromatic absorption, and its fluorescence properties are sensitive to the medium acidity and presence of the metal ions due to ICT and PET effects.

The design of this V-Er-O-Ni-K-As molecule was inspired by nice works of Professor Veronika Novakova and is dedicated to the celebration of her 40th Birthday. We wish Veronika new excellent achievements in the chemistry of pH- and ion-sensitive macrocyclic chromophores, and interesting adventures in science and in happy family life.

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Big Breakthrough: Greatly Decorated Diiminoisoindoles as Very Promising Precursors for Phthalocyanines

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ABSTRACT: New cooperation between the University of Pardubice and the Faculty of Pharmacy of Charles University, managed by V. N., is heading for an amazing breakthrough. The special substitution caused by the Ve-Ro-Ni-Ka decoration simplified and optimized the synthesis of compounds anybody only dream of. With this discovery, it will be possible to prepare a large variety of precursors for exceptional phthalocyanine's. These phthalocyanines will have many applications such as causing good health, good luck and wish fulfilment.

Thank you, Ve-Ro-Ni-Ka and Happy birthday!

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Light You Can't See Activates Singlet Oxygen – a Novel Report on an Ultimate Fire-side Cancer Killer System

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ABSTRACT: It has long been thought by others that the absorption of visible or UV light or even IR light is necessary for activating singlet oxygen to kill cancer cells [1] – but in this paper we prove that just the light from a microwave can activate the singlet oxygen in any house without the need to travel to specialist hospitals. And all that is needed are 4 brown eggs* in a bowl of plain water inside the microwave oven. Of course, there is no need to turn on the microwave – just the memory of it working previously is enough for it to radiate hidden, silent killing waves [2]. It is important to sit still near a fire in the house and relax the tissue with an appropriate beverage. Also necessary is a plate of 2 hotdogs covered with ketchup as the red of the ketchup attracts the waves from the eggs in the microwave. The singlet oxygen so activated will make its way directly to the site of the cancer and cancer cell annihilation will take place silently and painlessly. This setup is reminiscent of a premium quality hotel in Moscow.

Acknowledgements: We thank the editor of this special issue for providing us the opportunity to report this wonderful advance and congratulate one of his team members on her important coming-of-age event and also offer our thanks for a good laugh in Madrid from a footnote.

*Best if a week old; brown shells contain the natural protoporphyrin IX, a well-known singlet oxygen activator.

References:

- [1] Red-Emitting Dyes with Photophysical and Photochemical Properties Controlled by pH
Novakova, Veronika & Miletin, Miroslav & Kopecky, Kamil & Zimčík, Petr. (2011).. Chemistry (Weinheim an der Bergstrasse, Germany). 17. 14273-82. 10.1002/chem.201101123.
- [2] Unveiling the Hidden, Dark, and Short Life of a Vibronic State in a Boron Difluoride Formazanate Dye A. Melenbacher, J. S. Dhindsa, J. B. Gilroy, M. J. Stillman, Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 2019, 58, 15339.

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Severe Bone Ablation by Radical Photodynamic Treatment with Charged Azaphthalocyanine – a Non-randomized Phase II Clinical Trial on Volunteers with Presumably Fatal Osteosarcoma

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ABSTRACT: Photodynamic therapy (PDT) of tumors is well established in our group. Our very promising previous results with charged water-soluble (aza)phthalocyanine dyes *in vitro*¹ has led to an extensive work on this group of photosensitizers elucidating their mode of action.² With these inspiring results, we pursued their potential utilization in vascular-targeted PDT (VTP) which unveiled great success not only on *in vitro* models on several malignant cell lines but also on primary HUVECs. Even though, their activity against 3D multicellular spheroid cultures was ambiguous, they showed great potential on *in vivo* tumor-bearing mouse model.³ These accomplishments led to an unethical and nonlegal preclinical study on human volunteers suffering from osteosarcoma (they were paid well!). All volunteers were diagnosed with tumor after bone fracture and/or prolonged bone pain localized in their leg or arm. Tumor was confirmed by X-ray and subsequent biopsy, CT scan did not show any lesions in the chest area, PET bone scan was also clear indicating no other bone-lesions. Based on the *in vivo* results, irradiation was performed in VTP mode with cationic hydrophilic tetra(3,4-pyrido)porphyrine (5 min irradiation immediately after *i.v.* administration; 200 J/cm²; 0.1 μmol/kg) using 720 nm continuous wave diode laser coupled with optical fibers. Sadly, this VTP treatment have proven itself to be highly radical leading to large-scale vascular shutdown causing not only complete tumor necrosis, but also damage to surrounding bone tissue and adjacent periosteum. Oxidative stress and inflammation caused by dead tissue had triggered signal cascade inhibiting osteoblasts (decreased levels of osteoprotegerin and increased levels of RANKL and inhibition of Runx2-mediated osteoblast maturation) and activating osteoclasts (increased levels of IL-1, TRAP, NFATc1, v-ATPase, MMP and cathepsin K). Affected limbs had

to be fully surgically removed from all patients to prevent possible breakout of osteoporosis and metastatic spread of suppositious surviving tumor cells.

References:

¹ Machacek M., Demuth J., et al.; *J.Med.Chem.* 2016; DOI: 10.1021/acs.jmedchem.6b01140

² Kollar J., Machacek M., et al.; *J.Med.Chem.* 2020; DOI: 10.1021/acs.jmedchem.0c00481

³ Machacek M., Kozlikova M., et al.; unpublished results

Acknowledgement:

This work is purely fictional and fully dedicated to Veronicas 40th birthday. Warmest wishes to you on this very special day of yours! May you stay our great scientific inspiration! (Hope that our scientific work outlined in the abstract will never see itself coming true.)

The Efficient Azaphthalocyanine-free Dynamic Taste Therapy

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ABSTRACT: This work presents the application of emerging azaphthalocyanine-free dynamic taste therapy (AFDTT). AFDTT is currently the most successful way of solving various troubles. The mechanism of action is based on the employing of high excitation states. To succeed, it is essential to comply exactly with the following procedure. The multi-step chemical reaction requires many starting materials, however can it be carried out in one pot only.

Add approximately exactly:

- 500 g of middle gross-grinded seeds of *Triticum aestivum* (it is possible to replace maximally half of the amounts with grinded seeds of *Secale cereale*)
- 250 g of the purified crystallized infusion of *Beta vulgaris* var. *altissima*
- 2 spoons of pulverized roasted beans of *Theobroma cacao*
- 1 spoon of a special mixture prepared from grinded seeds of *Illicium verum*, *Pimpinella anisum*, *Elettaria cardamomum*, *Pimenta dioica*, lemon zest (*Citrus*), buds of *Syzygium aromaticum*, and bark of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*
- 2–3 spoons of sticky viscous liquid produced by *Apis mellifera*
- 20 g of sodium hydrogen carbonate
- 2 eggs of *Gallus gallus* f. *domestica*
- 250 mL of oily liquid obtained by pressing seeds of *Helianthus annuus*
- 500 mL of mother milk of *Bos primigenius* f. *domestica*
- dried fruits of *Vitis vinifera* ad libitum
- chopped seeds of *Juglans regia* ad libitum

Mix properly all ingredients in a pot using a husband. Then pour the mixture on a deeper reaction metal sheet. The reaction mixture should be heated at 180–200 °C approximately for 20–30 minutes in an oven (no microwaves are necessary). Already during the reaction (approx. 10 minutes before the reaction accomplishment) all members of the research team and laypersons in the surroundings will observe the effect of AFDTT on themselves.

The classic manifestation of the AFDTT is excitation, which reaches its maximum approx. 15 minutes after the finishing the reaction, during the cooling phase. The excitation may be accompanied by shouts of joy, strong absent-mindedness and drooling. The excitation state is usually followed by a long relaxation. The relaxation phase may be further extended and strengthened by the hot water extracts from *Camellia sinensis* or *Coffea arabica*.

Recommended dosage for administration: small pieces - quantum satis, especially in case of festive occasions like celebrations. Happy birthday!

- ♥ the person who is able to receive the correspondence
- ♠ the person, who is able to answer the correspondence

Investigation on Novel Complex of Veroniciium(II) – Synthesis, Characterization, In Vitro and In Vivo Results

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ABSTRACT: Recent progress in research in particle accelerator led to discovery of novel element with extraordinary properties – Veroniciium (Vr). [1] Anticipating unusual properties, we decided to focus more on its complexation properties. Tedious synthesis starting with treatment of sodium with water in sink at room temperature, overheating closed apparatus with dry THF (with subsequent extinguishing of reaction mixture, whole laboratory and one researcher with a powder extinguisher for 10 min) and innovative purification methods based on extraction of product from water bath of rotary evaporator (twice) yielded finally few precious milligrams of novel complex **1** with octacoordinated Vr(II) as central cation. Compound **1** absorbs the invisible cosmic irradiation with deep penetration through human tissues. After such activation, the compound is so excited that its molecules move extremely fast in the flask with speed exceeding speed of light. Treatment of immortalized cancer cells with even one activated molecule led to unprecedented exponential growth and subsequent differentiation into tissues and even organs. Keeping in mind extremely positive results from in vitro experiments, we decided to skip animal studies and to follow directly with intravenous application in humans. After a starting dose of 40 molecules, the experimental individual gained superpowers combining properties of all Marvel's characters being able to take care of two pre-school children, household keeping, mentoring PhD and undergrad students, teaching practical classes, writing research proposals of extraordinary quality, preparing manuscripts for Q1 journals and many others. Further investigations on the properties in the long-term administration of this experimental medication are running.

References:

[1] J. Lapešová et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 6.

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The Most Amazing Photosensitizer Ever

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ABSTRACT: In this work we describe the most amazing photosensitizers (PS) ever (an phthalocyanine, of course). This SuperPS has been developed by Veronika Novakova, the wizard of PDT, and consists of a macrocyclic core decorated with very muscular side arms (see Figure 1). Incredibly, it can produce singlet oxygen with 0.99 quantum yield, intense fluorescence in the near-infrared (NIR) for imaging also with 0.99 quantum yield. It is so strong that presents an IC₅₀ value of 1 pM, and can target all kind of cancers without any side effects, plus cardiovascular diseases, heavy stomach ache and even feet pain. Moreover, it is antidepressive, tastes like orange juice and gets you tipsy. All these properties will make the SuperPS a revolutionary drug that will transform the medical technology. We owe this great scientific discovery to a fantastic scientist, Veronika Novakova, who is also a great person and will continue doing fantastic research for the next decades. Happy birthday Veronika!!!

Figure 1. Structure of the SuperPS

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New Deterministic Approach to Rational Gingerbread Design for Use in 40-year-old Women for Well-being

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ABSTRACT: The present study investigated the effect of gingerbread composition on the well-being of women in the over-40 age group. The research was conducted in Torun - the capital of gingerbread, and the city of Nicolaus Copernicus (all gingerbread samples are available from the authors of this article). It has been shown that the length of time the gingerbread is allowed to rest in a warm place significantly impacts the well-being of women over 40. The longer the gingerbread is allowed to relax and rest, the less nervous and friendlier to the world the woman consuming it is. In addition, the amount of spices used is of great importance. It has been shown that a pinch of optimism, a sense of good humor and a little selfishness has not yet harmed any gingerbread. Considering this fact, it is recommended that patients over 40 include gingerbread in their diet just like this. Gingerbread can be covered with nothing in glaze or chocolate. The research clearly shows the positive effect of gingerbread coating on the behavior of the study group. The thicker the outer layer of gingerbread, the less the patient is concerned about what others say, which benefits her mental health. Finally, the effect of the amount of sugar and sweetness used to bake gingerbread on the study group was examined. The results unequivocally show that after the age of 40th, it is not necessary to be sweet and charming. It was proven that after crossing the magic number of 40, the patients are simply themselves. A summary of the study is presented in the attached picture, which shows individuals from the 40+ study population and the reference group.

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Veruene: A Generous Molecule with 40 Applications and Counting

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ABSTRACT: Herein, we will discuss about a different class of molecule called “Veruene” or V₄₀. This molecule is a sub-class of AzaPcs and possess several advantages. For instance, Veruene can be easily synthesised just by smiling and saying “Happy Birthday Veronika” with 100 % yield. Crystal structures can also be obtained by singing “Happy birthday song”. Veruene is a calm, extremely stable, helpful and friendly derivative with two derivatives (we may call it as Veruene’s daughters). However, Veruene’s stability is found to be inversely proportional to alcohol. With applications in at least 40 research areas, we have discussed 40 examples and authors wish Veruene to have a long, healthy, prosperous and excited life-time ahead.

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The Queen of the Rings: Dedicated to the Brilliant Young Designer of Phthalocyanine's Architectures

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ABSTRACT: Confucius said: "at the age of 15, a man should turn his thoughts to learning; at 30, to find a firm footing; at the age of 40, one must free oneself from doubt. So, it's time for great success. Good luck and prosperity, let every day be filled with interesting and creative tasks. New achievements, discoveries, victories together with the azaphthalocyanine group! More novel beautiful and useful for society macrocyclic rings!

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Phase I Clinical Trial of Vr(II) Complex: The First Application in Pediatric Population

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ABSTRACT: Recently, new discoveries on the novel element Veronidium (Vr) described excellent effects of its complexes on human beings receiving superpowers. [1] The aim of this follow-up study was to explore efficacy and safety of these complexes in pediatric population. Phase I clinical trial was conducted in two kids of different age and gender coming from very sensitive parents. Just a single dose of few molecules had immediate calming effect on both experimental subjects and led to 100% reduction of manifestation of misbehaving, disobedience and back talking. The effect persisted even after withdrawal for several days, however, for long term control of the symptoms, repeated doses were necessary. Application of the complex **1** to kids also increased substantially quality of life of both parents. It has been assessed by McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire and improvement in all subscales (physical, psychological, existential, social, environment, cognition, health care and burden) has been observed. Application of the complex **1** to the children also delayed manifestation of the child-induced DNA damage in the brain of mother[2] (unfortunately only temporarily).

References:

[1] P. Zimčík et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 16.

[2] K. Vávrová et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 4.

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Novel Synthesis of Universally Sensing Vr^{2+} Based Azaphthalocyanine Compounds

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ABSTRACT: Following the previous discovery and synthesis of Veronidium (Vr^{2+}) based complexes [1, 2], this work features sensoric azaphthalocyanine-based macrocyclic sensor (Fig. 1) whose sensitivity towards all things bright and wonderful such as new ideas, best solutions, happy energy, and a multitude of cheer. In addition, on sensing of the above-tested entities, there is also observed radiation of an enormous amount of positive energy, love, care, concern, understanding and kindness. The results of photophysical experiments conducted to measure the increase in fluorescence (Fig. 2) towards the sensory activity and the quantum yields (Fig. 3) were mind-blowing! We are very grateful for the presence and contribution of these complexes towards the wonderful life of everyone in the AzaPc group owing to the marvellous properties of Vr^{2+} . We wish the best of all that unfolds to the extremely excellent Vr^{2+} , a very Happy Birthday! 😊

Figure 1 Design of AzaPc Vr^{2+} sensoric complex

Figure 2 Increase in fluorescence with analyte

Figure 3 Quantum yield of Vr^{2+} sensoric complex.

References:

- [1] J. Lapešová et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 6.
- [2] P. Zimčík et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 16.

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Ghost in a Service of Science: A Helpful Tool or a Curse?

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^a Laboratory room 2236, from your sight the magic place behind the door next to the desk (or behind the chair, or in the opposite corner from couch of the office your often occupying, OR two floors under your official office, depending on where you currently fill the working vacuum).

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ABSTRACT: Even though scientific highly-ranked journals do not usually report about paranormal activities, we decided to make an exception and closely observed and examined a remarkable phenomenon occurring in our working environment. To our further knowledge there is no other place in the world such an appearance would be reported, therefore, atypically for a chemist research group, this is a case report.

Ever since we started our projects, strange things are going on here. Things are moving, experiments are done, new topics, and also, money are coming out of nowhere! These helpful, nevertheless spooky features are more frequented as the deadline for any article is coming. Suddenly, all graphics look differently, unified, smoother, elegant, even telling just the information we wanted! (Sometimes even the opposite info we thought we prove all along.) Overnight, our English is rapidly getting more scientific, facts are connected, and time to time the whole article makes sense. Also, there is a phone number to an unknown place, where we can call, even Friday evening!!, and where we can gain rare, precious knowledges about new techniques or equipment running in our lab for decades, which nobody else knows! To be honest in our experiences, only sometimes it is useful call but on the other hand it is always a cheerful one!

Despite the fact, that evaluation looks quite promising with positive effect on all our projects. There are obviously drawbacks, too. We noticed a higher level of compulsory tasks for us appearing from no reason, the new experiments must often be done by us, and considering the calls, they are often both-way causing multiple stress by not knowing the question on random facts, which never even appeared in our mind. (Not mentioning the funny noises in background, scream included :D) Overall status of our lab members is positive though and we come in agreement to wish longer appearance of this nice ghost in our lives!!

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Identification and Recognition of an Outstanding Phthalocyanine Measurement-performing Women in Porphyrin Science

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ABSTRACT: Phthalocyanines are great. Veronika Novakova is known to make great measurements with phthalocyanines. Veronika Novakova is great. The other way around is also a scientific fact.

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INTRODUCTION

Counting years are an excellent way to have regular opportunities to eat and drink together, especially when the sun has achieved a full rotation around the earth since a previous birthday. It is therefore highly valuable to celebrate the fourthiest rotation of the sun around the Earth since the birthday of Veronika Novakova because Veronika is great.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Dear Veronika, I really wish you an excellent birthday, and so much happiness ! It is good to have you in the Por&Pcs community, not only for the occasions to chat from time to time in ICPPs, but also for your kindness and your science, plus the demonstration that you can do all of that and be yourself. Take care of you ! The best years are ahead, for sure !

EXPERIMENTAL

All experiments have been carefully completed. Congresses have been joined together, including coffees breaks and all types of lunches and diners.

CONCLUSION

Happy Birthday Veronika !

Veronicium: The New Promising Photocatalyst

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ABSTRACT: After breakthrough discovery of new element *Veronicium* (Vr) by Lapešová et al.,¹ multiple research groups are interesting in study of this amazing element. In this paper photocatalytic properties of Vr (II) complexes were studied. It was discovered that tetrapyrroldiopyrroline complex with Vr (II) (TPyPzVr) showed unique behavior after irradiation with light at 640 nm. TPyPzVr was excited by absorption of light, which is common feature for phthalocyanines family, however the relaxing pathway was completely new and against all already published papers. One positron was released during relaxation from excited state of TPyPzVr and this particle was able to magically power and direct wide range of reaction and thanks to that it saves lot of chemist's time. The practical usage of TPyPzVr was already tested in cooperation with company Omarap (Half-horse city, Czech republic) for decontamination of waste air from pollutants. Decontamination products were carbon dioxide, water, and n-hexane. The las one was collected and subsequently used as fuel. Follow up study showed that incidence of pulmonary diseases in nearby area decreased by 40 % in comparison of 6 years old data. This new system of filtration of air based on TPyPzVr (1 ‰ mol) immobilized on nanofibers can improve quality of life for large amount of people.

References:

¹ J. Lapešová et al., *J. Unpublishable Results*, **2023**, 2023 (1), 6.

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